

MADRASAH DINIAH AS MEDIA TEACHING AND LEARNING ISLAMIC MODERATION VALUES AT *QUR'AN* LEARNING CENTERS

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Submitted
2022-07-07

Accepted
2022-10-23

Published
2022-12-01

OPEN ACCESS

Abstract

Madrasah diniyah has an essential role in educating the younger generation concerning instilling Islamic values from an early age. Moderation Islam (*wasathiyah* Islam) has now become a school of Islamic thought that has become a discourse. This research aimed to interpret *madrasah diniyah* education as a medium for teaching and learning Islamic moderation values to students of *Taman Pendidikan Al-Quran* (*Qur'an* Learning Center). The research method used qualitative. This research was conducted at Baiturrahman Mosque, Sleman, Yogyakarta. The subjects were three *Qur'an* Learning Center teachers of the Baiturrahman Mosque. This research used data collection techniques through interviews, observations, and secondary sources. The data analysis technique used in the form of content analysis techniques. Based on the results of the research, it was found that early *madrasah diniyah* education can be used as a medium of teaching and learning to instill Islamic moderation values.

Keywords: *madrasah diniyah*; Islamic teaching; Islamic learning.

Abstrak

Madrasah diniyah memiliki peran penting dalam mendidik generasi muda dalam kaitannya menanamkan nilai-nilai Islam sejak dini. Moderasi Islam (*wasathiyah* Islam) telah menjadi aliran pemikiran Islam yang menjadi pembicaraan. Tujuan penelitian adalah untuk menginterpretasikan pendidikan *madrasah diniyah* sebagai media pengajaran dan pembelajaran nilai-nilai moderasi Islam pada santri *Taman Pendidikan Al-Quran*. Metode penelitian yang digunakan adalah metode kualitatif. Penelitian dilakukan di Masjid Baiturrahman, Sleman, Yogyakarta. Subjek penelitian adalah tiga guru santri *Taman Pendidikan Al-Quran* Masjid Baiturrahman. Penelitian menggunakan teknik pengumpulan data melalui wawancara, observasi, dan sumber sekunder. Teknik analisis data yang digunakan berupa teknik analisis konten. Berdasarkan hasil penelitian, ditemukan bahwa pendidikan *madrasah diniyah* dapat dijadikan sebagai media pengajaran dan pembelajaran dalam menanamkan nilai-nilai moderasi Islam.

Kata Kunci: *madrasah diniyah*; pengajaran Islam; pembelajaran Islam.